

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

UV Method Of Development For Estimation Of Losartan In Bulk & Marketed Formulation

Pardeshi J. G^{*1}, Sonawane K.A², Dashpute S.N³, Wagh S.V⁴

^{1,2,3}Matoshri Institute of pharmacy, Dhanore, Yeola

⁴Swami Institute of pharmacy, Mungase, Malegaon

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 21 July 2024

Accepted: 24 July 2024

Published: 28 July 2024

Keywords:

Losartan, UV Spectroscopy,
pH Meter.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.13118404

ABSTRACT

Attempts were made to develop UV method for simultaneous estimation of losartan from tablet. The mobile phase methanol:water(70:30 ratio). pKa was found drug 5.5. pH of drug was found to be 3. Selection of wavelength found to 208nm. The linearity, accuracy, precision, range, LOD, LOQ was within the limit as specified by the ICH guidelines. Hence these method simple economic precise accurate and reproducible.

INTRODUCTION

DRUG PROFILE

Chemical Name – [2-butyl-5-chloro-3-[[4-[2-(2H-tetrazol-5-yl) phenyl] phenyl] methyl] imidazol-4-yl] methanol

Structure –

Molecular Formula -C₂₂H₂₃ClN₆O

Brand Name-Losar-25

Relative Molecular Mass -422.9 gram/moles

Solubility-Soluble in Water, Methanol.

pKa-5.5

Pharmacology-Losartan is an angiotensin II receptor blocker used to treat hypertension, diabetic nephropathy, and to reduce the risk of stroke. Losartan has a long duration of action as it is given once daily. Patients taking losartan should be regularly monitored for hypotension, renal function, and potassium levels.

Experimental Work-

MATERIALS AND INSTRUMENTS

***Corresponding Author:** Pardeshi J. G

Address: Matoshri Institute of pharmacy, Dhanore, Yeola

Email ✉: jjyotshanap.51@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Table 6.1: List of chemicals

Chemicals	Source
Losartan	Swapnroop Research Pvt Ltd. Aurangabad.
Distilled Water	Prepared in Lab (S' COP)
Methanol	Shodh Adavntech Aurangabad

Table 6.2: List of Equipment

Equipment	Company
Single beam UV-Visible Spectrophotometer range 200-400 1cm quartz cell	Lab India
pH METER	LABINDIA, PHAN
Sonicator	Ultrasonic

FORMULATION –

Dosage Form – Tablet Brand Name – Losar-25

The Marketed Formulation Contain 25mg

Result and Discussion-

Selection of Wavelength –

Tablet powder equivalent to 10 mg of Losartan was dissolved in small quantity of diluent in a 10

mL volumetric flask and final volume was made up to 10 ml with same. Sonicated for 10 minutes. Then the absorbance of the solution (after suitable dilution) was measured at 208nm using UV/visible spectrophotometer (Lab India) against diluent as a blank.

Analysis of Marketed Formulation –

No.	ID	Mode	A		Assay (%)
			208.00nm		
1	Sample	Absorbance	1-	0.875	100.9%
			2-	0.872	
			3-	0.873	
2	Standard	Absorbance	0.865		

Validation of UV Method –

Linearity and Range –

Concentration in µg/ml	Absorbance
2	0.230
4	0.359
6	0.539
8	0.710
10	0.869

Linearity curve for Losartan

Linear Regression Data for calibration curve –

Parameters	Results
λ max (nm)	208 nm
Beer's limit	2 – 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
Regression equation	$y=0.0815x + 0.0527$
Correlation equation	$R^2 = 0.9976$
Slope	0.0815
Intercept	0.0527

Precision –

Intra – day precision studies.

No.	Concentration in $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Absorbance
I (11.30AM)	3	0.352
	5	0.432
	7	0.702
II (14.30PM)	3	0.349
	5	0.430
	7	0.701

Concentration in $\mu\text{g/ml}$	3	5	7
%RSD	0.60%	0.32%	0.10%

Intra – Day precision parameter with % RSD

Inter – day precision studies.

No.	Concentration in $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Absorbance
Day 1 (20/06/22)	3	0.352
	5	0.432
	7	0.702
Day 2 (21/06/22)	3	0.358
	5	0.444
	7	0.713

Concentration in $\mu\text{g/ml}$	3	5	7
%RSD	1.2%	1.9%	1.1%

Inter– Day precision parameter with % RSD

LOD & LOQ of Losartan –

Parameter	$\mu\text{g/mL}$
LOD (Limit of Detection)	1.68
LOQ Limit of Quantification)	5.094

CONCLUSION

The simple spectrophotometric method for determination of Losartan has been developed and validated as per ICH guidelines. The developed method is found to be sensitive, accurate and reproducible and can be used for the routine quality control analysis of Losartan in bulk and pharmaceutical formulations. Attempts were made to develop spectrophotometric for estimation of

Losartan. The spectrophotometric methods were developed for estimation. For the spectrophotometric methods, Methanol was used as solvent. The wavelength used for Losartan 208nm. The spectrophotometric methods were validated according to the ICH guidelines. The linearity, precisions, LOD, LOQ by the spectrophotometric method were within the limit as specified by the ICH guidelines. Hence the

methods were found to be simple, accurate, precise, economic and reproducible. so the proposed methods can be used for the routine quality control analysis of Venlafaxine in bulk drug as well as in formulations.

REFERENCE

1. Douglas A. Skoog, F. James Holler, Timothy A. Nieman, "Principles of Instrumental Analysis", 5th Edition, 2005, Saunders College Publishing. Harcourt Brace College Publishers, p; 725-750
2. A.H.Backett, J.B. Stanlake," Practical Pharmaceutical Chemistry "4th edition, part II, CBS Publisher and Distributors, Delhi, 2001, p;255-280.
3. Willard, "Instrumental Methods of Analysis "7th edition, CBS Publisher and Distributors, Delhi. P;514
4. Chatwal GR, Sham KA, High performance liquid chromatography. In: Instrumental methods of chemical analysis. 5th ed. Mumbai: Himalaya Publishing house: 2002. P:2.626-2.636.
5. ISO/IEC 17025. International standard: General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories. Geneva, Switzerland (1999).
6. U.S. Food and Drug Administration. Technical Review Guide: Validation of Chromatographic Methods. Rockville, MD: Center for Drug Evaluation and Research (CDER) (1993).
7. Frank Settle. Handbook of Instrumental techniques for analytical chemistry. NJ: Prentice Hall PTR: 1997. P:17,19,56,57.
8. U.S. Food and Drug Administration. Industry Draft Guidance Analytical Procedures and Methods Validation Chemistry, Manufacturing, and Controls Documentation (Aug.2000).
9. USP 32 – NF 27, General Chapter 1225, Validation of Compendial Methods, 2009.
10. USP 32 – NF 27, General Chapter 1226, Verification of Compendial Method, 2009.
11. Nash R.A,Wachter A.H. Pharmaceutical Process Validation; 3rd edition, Vol; 129, Marcel Dekker, Inc 2003,542- 559
12. ICH; Technical Requirements for the Registration of Pharmaceuticals for Human Use, Validation of analytical procedures, ICH- Q2A, 1995.
13. ICH Technical Requirements for the Registration of Pharmaceuticals for Human Use, Validation of analytical procedures: Methodology, ICH- Q2B, 1997.
14. ICH; Validation of analytical procedures Text and methodology. Q2(R1). Fed Regist 2005;
15. Rockville, Maryland, the United States Pharmacopeia 25/National Formulary 20, ch. 1225, The United States Pharmacopeia Convention, 2002 2256 – 2259 .
16. Stability testing of New Drug Substances and Products, International Conference on Harmonization (ICH), Geneva, 1993, Q1E
17. www.regulatory.com, Validation of assays and tests method for Pharmaceutical laboratory, by R.V. Sarrio and J. Silvestre, 2005 Conference on Hamonization (ICH), Geneva, 1993, Q1E
18. John W. Dolan, Stability indicating Assays, LCGC North America, Volume 4,2002, 346-349.

HOW TO CITE: Pardeshi J. G*, Sonawane K.A, Dashpute S.N, Wagh S.V, UV Method Of Development For Estimation Of Losartan In Bulk & Marketed Formulation, Int. J. of Pharm. Sci., 2024, Vol 2, Issue 7, 2029-2032. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13118404>

